

THE DIGITAL ECONOMY: TENDENCIES AND PROSPECTS FOR BUSINESS CHANGE

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Mahkamboyeva Ozoda

Jizzakh State Pedagogical Institute

Foreign language (English) in preschool and primary education

2nd year student

Norpulatova Shakhnoza

Jizzakh State Pedagogical Institute

Foreign language (English) in preschool and primary education

2nd year student

Annotation: *This article discusses the role of the digital economy in human life, business change trends and prospects.*

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In recent years, the importance of advanced technologies and innovations in economic development has increased. The latest technologies in production and business processes can increase efficiency. The latest technology is human penetration into all new areas and areas of activity traditional approaches and working methods will change. The emergence of information and communication technologies (ICT) The emergence and spread of the global economy has had such an impact that a new phenomenon - the digital economy - has emerged. Influenced by information and communication technologies people's lifestyles are changing, users The relationship between the two has changed - different geographical areas, activities networking and connecting people in other areas the opportunity arose. It was the foundation of the digital economy rapid growth of information communication. The impact of digital technology is global, too. also felt locally. Digital economy is a new development the rapid growth of the global economy as a combination of output is a growing part.

Nowadays, the digital economy and many related effective technologies, including e-commerce and e-business, are rapidly entering our lives. For this reason, in order to further accelerate the development of the state and society, the leadership of the republic has made a number of important decisions. For example,

in his Address to the Oliy Majlis on the most important priorities for 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 25, 2020 said the following about the development of the digital economy in our country: In order to nurture high spirituality and culture, to continue the work we have begun to form a competitive economy and to raise it to a new, modern level, I propose to name 2020 the "Year of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy" in our country. In addition, in pursuance of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 19, 2018 No PF-5349 "On measures to further develop the field of information technology and communications" 1, as well as for the introduction of digital economy in public administration in the country In order to create conditions for the rapid development of modern information technologies, as well as to ensure information security, the Cabinet of Ministers on August 31, 2018 approved the "Additional These measures include the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PP-3832 dated 03.07.2018 "On measures to develop the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan." .

The most important tasks for the further development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan are:

- ✓Cryptocurrencies for investment and business diversification →□activities in the field of turnover, including mining, smart contract, consulting, issue, exchange, storage, distribution, management, insurance, crowdfunding, as well as the introduction of blockchain technology and development

- ✓Training of qualified personnel with practical work skills in the production and use of blockchain technologies.

- ✓Ensuring close cooperation between government agencies and businesses in the implementation of innovative ideas, technologies and developments for the further development of the digital economy.

- ✓Comprehensive development of cooperation with international and foreign organizations in the field of cryptocurrency activities and blockchain technologies and the involvement of highly qualified foreign specialists working in the field of production.

- ✓Creating a legal framework for the introduction of blockchain technologies, taking into account foreign experience².

Given the global trends and developments in foreign policy, Uzbekistan faces the challenge of global competitiveness and national security, and the development of the digital economy in the country plays an important and decisive role in addressing this issue. Some elements of the digital economy are already working successfully in our country. Nowadays, given the mass transfer of documents and

communications to digital means, the issuance of electronic signatures, communication with the state is also transferred to electronic platforms. The authors of this handbook analyze the reasons for digitalization, consider the causes and goals of the digital economy and e-commerce, and analyze the methods and technologies that support the digital economy. Digitization of economic processes is becoming a comprehensive trend that covers not only the direct information and communication network, but also all areas of economic activity in the country. The digital economy revolution is also having a strong impact on e-commerce, digital agriculture, “smart” grid systems, driverless transport, and personalized healthcare. In particular, the digital economy is an innovative idea, and this idea was expressed by the World Bank in its 2016 World Development Report 2016: Digital Dividends. In this context, individual companies, regions, countries and their associations are actively involved in the formation and implementation of strategic decisions in the digital economy, striving to provide new emerging long-term competitive advantages in the markets of new technologies, goods and services. is a unique virtual environment that complements reality. Western experts agree that digital technology will not work if the relationship between economic entities and management is not regulated. changes behavior. E-marketing is also gradually approaching the essence of economic interactions, the main driving force that forces everyone to engage in economic interactions - needs. The management process of e-commerce in the digital economy (through professional staff) is a computerized system of interaction management, which carries out a wide range of work on the active use of electronic information to meet the growing needs of mankind. For example, it provides for the prediction, planning, organization, execution, control and coordination of system activities.

Digital economy is a new modern form of management, in which the main factor of production and management is a large set of data in digital form and the process of their processing. The practical application of the obtained results will allow to achieve much greater efficiency than traditional forms of management. Examples include a variety of automated manufacturing processes, 3D technology, cloud technologies, remote medical services, the development and delivery of products using smart technologies, and the storage and sale of a variety of goods.

The fact that our country, like many developed countries, has chosen the path of developing the digital economy opens up new directions in the field of information technology and electronic document management in general. The shift of society to digital technologies is due to the improvement of the quality of the

world wide web and the development of communication systems. As a result, it has become possible to share and collect large amounts of data, which in turn allows the collected information to be processed, predicted, made to make informed decisions, and benefited in a variety of ways. The development of e-commerce in Uzbekistan, which is part of the digital economy, can be divided into two periods: before 2015 and beyond. Until 2015, our country has been actively working to develop and prepare a regulatory framework. In 2015, the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted the Concept for the development of e-commerce for 2015-2018, and in the medium term to develop e-commerce. identified key areas, expansion of the competitive environment, creation of modern infrastructure and creation of additional jobs, as well as forms and ways to further improve the legislation on e-commerce.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

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